

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) CuCl2DMSO2

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: CuCl2DMSO2

Bond precision: S- C = 0.0019 A Wavelength=1.34139

Cell: a=7.9456 (7) b=11.4897 (11) c=11.3619 (11)
 alpha=90 beta=90 gamma=90

Temperature: 120 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1037.26 (17)	1037.26 (17)
Space group	P n m a	P n m a
Hall group	-P 2ac 2n	-P 2ac 2n
Moiety formula	C4 H12 Cl2 Cu O2 S2	C4 H12 Cl2 Cu O2 S2
Sum formula	C4 H12 Cl2 Cu O2 S2	C4 H12 Cl2 Cu O2 S2
Mr	290.71	290.70
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.862	1.861
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	16.811	16.812
F000	588.0	588.0
F000'	582.68	
h, k, lmax	10, 14, 14	10, 14, 14
Nref	1253	1250
Tmin, Tmax	0.147, 0.502	0.036, 0.140
Tmin'	0.066	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.036 Tmax=0.140
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.998 Theta (max)= 60.578

R(reflections)= 0.0234 (1241)

wR2(reflections)=
0.0617 (1250)

S = 1.130

Npar= 57

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

PLAT094_ALERT_2_C Ratio of Maximum / Minimum Residual Density 2.16 Report

Author Response: The min and max values of the residual electron density are 0.41 and - they are too low to be caused by either an unaccounted twinning or missing atom

PLAT911_ALERT_3_C Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600 2 Report
0 4 0, 0 6 0,

Author Response: These two reflexes are missed due to detector overflow.

Alert level G

ABSMU01_ALERT_1_G Calculation of _exptl_absorpt_correction_mu
not performed for this radiation type.
PLAT004_ALERT_5_G Polymeric Structure Found with Maximum Dimension 1 Info
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G Tentative Bond Valency for CuI (II) . 2.03 Info
PLAT802_ALERT_4_G CIF Input Record(s) with more than 80 Characters 2 Info
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G Missing FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta (Min) [Deg]= 5.91 Note
0 1 1,
PLAT913_ALERT_3_G Missing # of Very Strong Reflections in FCF 1 Note
0 4 0,
PLAT961_ALERT_5_G Dataset Contains no Negative Intensities Please Check
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 3.011 Note
Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 2.05 or SHELX Weight 5.46

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
2 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
8 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

1 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
1 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
3 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
1 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
4 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

